

Agreed portfolio of community tools

Deliverable D1.1

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Work package in charge: *WP1 Governance, Engagement & long-term Sustainability*

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

This document reports on shared software at the initial stage of ESIWACE, identifying different level of governance and analysing how it is applied in the single cases, listing stakeholders, steering and user groups and focusing on the role of the latters and on their interaction within the project. This activity is to be interpreted as a first step toward the ultimate goal of proposing/adjusting governance rules for certain software, when/where missing. Particular emphasis is therefore placed on the services guaranteeing more efficient exchange with the community. In view of the activities to come, we furthermore propose to create a 'living' software list to regularly collect information on software with potential to be shared among the European Climate modelling and NWP community, to serve as a valuable screening instrument to the ESIWACE governance.

2. Conclusion & Results

A portfolio of shared software was compiled based on use and support activities within ESIWACE. For each software we indicated user community, support and governance structure and confirmed the heterogeneous level of maturity of the list items (the community code coupling software OASIS, the Climate Data Operators CDO, the I/O and post-processing software XIOS, the workflow engine and meta-scheduler Cylc, the ocean modelling framework NEMO, the Earth system model EC-Earth/OpenIFS), justifying different initiatives to be undertaken to enhance user-drivenness.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support of the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	Yes
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	No
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	No

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	Yes
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes

Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	Yes
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	Yes
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

This document aims at informing on the state of shared, common software at the beginning of ESIWACE (month 6), by indicating stakeholders, users and steering structure. After introducing the methodology categorizing the software and explaining the function and aim of this document, a list was compiled including: the community code coupling software OASIS, the Climate Data Operators CDO, the I/O and post-processing software XIOS, the workflow engine and meta-scheduler Cylc, the ocean modelling framework NEMO, the Earth system model EC-Earth/OpenIFS. For each software item, the following aspects are indicated in this document: Name, Short Description, Current version(s) of the software in the frame of ESIWACE (as of Feb 2016), Developer Institutions, Documentation repository, Contact, Target community (type, size, and geographic distribution), Governance model, Foreseen developments, User support, and Funding model, alongside a table summarizing the funding history of each in terms of projects.

A concluding paragraph analyses the level of existing governance, explains how the resulting information will be exploited, and introduces the upcoming compilation of an additional software list to complement this document as a support instrument to the ESIWACE governance.

The lead authors wrote the actual document, introducing the methodology, putting together the contributions from other participants, and presenting summary and outlook.

The beneficiaries other than the lead author participated - to different extent - to the definition of the methodology and provided details on the software they manage.

5. References (*Bibliography*)

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NEMO Consortium Agreement: http://www.nemo-ocean.eu/Media/Files/NEMO_Consortium.Agreement.pdf

E. Maisonnave, S. Masson Ocean/sea-ice macro task parallelism in NEMO
<http://cerfacs.fr/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/GLOBC-Maisonnave-022015-ocean1.pdf>

6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Dissemination

Not applicable. This deliverable analyses the state of shared software at the beginning of ESIWACE.

Peer reviewed articles

No papers directly related to this deliverable nor with the Task 1.1.2 Governance on community software have been published at this initial stage (month 6) in the frame of ESIWACE.

6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This deliverable will be available online in the project website as well as distributed within and beyond the Consortium i.e. in first place to the Supporting Partners.

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

None.

9. Efforts for this deliverable

Person-months spent on this deliverable:

Beneficiary	Person-months	Period covered	Names of scientists involved, including third parties (if appropriate) and their gender (f/m)
DKRZ	<0.1		J. Biercamp (m), K.Fieg (f)
ECMWF	<0.1		P. Bauer (m)
CNRS-IPSL	0.5	11/15-02/16	S. Jousaume (f)
MPG	<0.1		R. Budich (m)
CERFACS	<0.1		S. Valcke (f)
BSC			
STFC			
MET O	<0.1		M. Carter (m)
UREAD			
SMHI	<0.1		U. Fladrich (m)
ICHEC			
CMCC			
DWD			
SEAGATE			
BULL			
ALLINEA			
Total	~1		

The preparation of this deliverable involved the staff mentioned above, besides having the beneficiaries involved in agreeing on the methodology, partly introduced in the project design

phase. Beneficiaries other than CNRS-IPSL (lead author) contributed with less than 0.1 PM and are therefore not indicated.

10. Sustainability

10.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

Communication and exchange on software is essential. The project lead and partners should always be aware of community needs and receive continuous feedback to guide developments and create/adapt support services. Where missing, software governance should be implemented, where already in place, supported. As climate modelling and NWP will outlive ESIWACE, it is important to sustain long-term governance of the software portfolio.

10.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This deliverable involves software involved in activities distributed over the whole project. Support on, training for and integration of state-of-the-art software are defined in WP2 and WP3.

11. Dissemination activities

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Number	Total funding amount	Type of audience reached In the context of all dissemination & communication activities ('multiple choices' is possible)	Estimated number of persons reached
Diffusion through the project mailing list and the ENES mailing list, publication on the project website	//	//	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [Scientific Community (higher education, Research)] [Industry] 	Ca.250 contact persons

Annex: Agreed portfolio of community tools

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1. Introduction

The Centre of Excellence ESIWACE aims at improving efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms. The project focuses on the aspects of Scalability and Usability of model codes and modeling tools and on the Exploitability of storage supports. The design, development, uses, and management of software plays a fundamental role in all projects activities. In order to avoid redundant re-development, ESIWACE aims at strengthening the sharing of software and of its development.

This document aims at informing on the state of shared software at the beginning of ESIWACE (M6), by indicating stakeholders, users and steering structure.

2. Methodology

Based on the activities foreseen in the ESIWACE Description of Action, in particular on the nature of interaction with community users, software could be grouped into four different categories. A first group encompasses “mature”, shared, common codes for most of which service to the community is explicitly defined within the project; a second group includes software involved in testing and/or benchmarking activities (to the results of which the community should have access) that is likely to be progressively taken up by groups, i.e. to become community tool; a third group involves newly developed codes, a fourth considers other software used by several groups within the community, independently from its origin.

This document presents codes belonging to the first group: a portfolio of software, models and modeling tools, selected based on their use, common to several European institutions in the weather and climate modeling community. Most of this software is involved in the planned support service activities as per the ESIWACE DoA, WP2 and WP3. This document depicts for different items, the state, advancement, funding model, and level of sharing at the time of the start of the project, as well as the foreseen evolution during ESIWACE. The EC past and present support includes several projects involving activities at different stages of the software lifetime, from inception to development, maintenance, adaptation to different platforms, provision of service to users, broadening of the users base. In many cases ESIWACE activities build directly upon the legacy of the FP7 Infrastructure projects IS-ENES (2009-2013) and IS-ENES2 (2013-2017).

By offering a picture of the common software landscape as of February 2016, this text aims at working as an instrument to support the governance of ESIWACE in its initial, crucial phase. ESIWACE Tasks 1.1.2 and 1.1.3 will moreover benefit from this information and further pursue the above presented methodology.

The software chosen comprehends the model codes NEMO and EC-EARTH/OpenIFS and the tools OASIS, CDO, XIOS, and Cylc.

For each software item, the following aspects are indicated in this document:

- Name
- Short Description
- Current version(s) of the software in the frame of ESIWACE (as of Feb 2016)
- Developers
- Documentation repository
- Contact
- Target community (type, size, and geographic distribution)

- Governance model
- Foreseen developments (specify which activities are implemented within ESIWACE)
- User support (including user groups, mailing lists etc.)
- Funding model

Type of software	Project	other project	PRISM	IS-ENES phase 1	IS-ENES 2	ESIWACE
Modelling Tools	OASIS	D	D	D/S	D/S/N	D/S
	CDO	D		S	S	
	XIOS	D		D	D	D/S
	CYLC	D			N	D/S
Models	NEMO	D		D/S	S	D/S
	EC-EARTH/OPENIFS	D			S	D/S

Table 1: Models and tools involved in ESIWACE activities and their development (D), support (S) or networking (N) funding history. PRISMS, IS-ENES, ISENES2 are European projects supporting research infrastructures (FP5, FP7, and FP7, respectively).

3. Software list

3.1. OASIS

Name: OASIS

Short Description:

Community **code coupling software**

Current version(s) of the software in the frame of ESIWACE (as of Feb 2016):

OASIS3-MCT_3.0

Developer:

Cerfacs Centre Européen de Recherche et de Formation Avancée en Calcul Scientifique (Toulouse, France) and CNRS Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (Paris, France)

Documentation available at:

<https://verc.enes.org/oasis/oasis-dedicated-user-support-1/documentation>

Contact:

Sophie Valcke (CERFACS) oasishelp@cerfacs.fr

Target community (type, size, and geographic distribution):

Developers and users of climate coupled models. More than 70 climate-modelling groups worldwide, among which about 40 in Europe.

Governance model:

The Governance model, elaborated in the frame of IS-ENES2 represents a first stage of a lightweight governance model -with users playing a primary role- in course of implementation (as of Feb 2016). For details, refer to the section 'foreseen developments' below.

Foreseen developments (specify which activities are implemented within ESIWACE):

Technical aspects: OASIS3-MCT offers fully parallel regridding and distributed exchanges of coupling fields between the component codes of a climate model. Low-intrusiveness, portability and flexibility are OASIS3-MCT key design concepts. After compilation OASIS3-MCT is a coupling library to be linked to the component models. OASIS3-MCT supports coupling of 2D logically- rectangular fields but 3D fields and 1D fields expressed on unstructured grids are also supported using a one dimension degeneration of the structures. Thanks to MCT, all transformations, including regridding, are performed in parallel on the set of source or target component processes and all coupling exchanges are now executed in parallel directly between the component processes via Message Passing Interface (MPI). OASIS3-MCT also supports file I/O using netcdf. However OASIS3-MCT does not perform parallel calculation of the regridding weights and addresses per se. Different tools can be used off-line to pre-calculate these weights and addresses in parallel. This functionality will be needed in the coupler to support adaptive grids. In the longer term, the development of parallel calculation of the regridding weights and addresses or the integration of an existing library offering this functionality, e.g. ESMF (Hill et al. 2004) or OpenPALM (Duchaine et al. 2013), should be considered.

Another example of strategic evolution is the possible long-term convergence with the IO server XIOS: the main functions of an I/O server and of a coupler (i.e. communication and regridding of data) are very similar and it is likely that these could be integrated into a converged solution.

Governance aspects: A community governance strategy is needed, on the long term, to address the foreseen jump in complexity of the coupling problem on exascale and the associated increase of performance required. Essentially, ESMs will have to increase parallelism and this needs to be supported by the component coupling infrastructure.

The proposed community governance model was initially elaborated in the frame of IS-ENES2 activities and is based on the results of a user survey (2015, 10 OASIS European users) and on the experience of the main developers (more than 15 years managing OASIS software and interacting with its users).

The survey covered strategic requirements (opportunity of sharing software at different time scales/development stages), appetite for engagement (necessity of community governance, i.e. top-down) and possible model, funding model (individual contributions vs research infrastructure sustainable funds), need for more software sharing before possible governance. The outcome of the survey highlighted several fundamental aspects to be implemented in the coupler governance. We report the most relevant ones here:

- Benefit from sharing and desire to extend it to other parts of the infrastructure (IO, post-processing, monitoring).
- Importance of strengthening user groups and user/developer communication to be included in the governance.
- Lack of readiness of the groups to enhance own involvement in development and management of the coupler or of other software.
- Consensus on rejecting top-down actions enforcing the sharing, due to lack of readiness to commit and of conviction on the effectiveness. Accepting current bottom-up approach, which has proven to work, with different groups developing different tools with some of these tools, deserving to become community tools, naturally emerging given adequate networking is ensured.
- Funding models: "one group develops the coupling software with the different partners contributing money to this group" deemed as too risky. "Different partners contribute efforts to the software

development, this resulting in a geographically distributed software development” not favoured either as effective multi-site development is considered difficult (OASIS3-MCT is a successful example of distributed development, but OASIS4 is not). Community prefers to rely on some form of externally funded research infrastructure, ideally coordinated via ENES, to ensure networking and additional funding for the tools identified as community tools.

The resulting proposed governance model is a lightweight governance structure structured as follows:

An external advisory board with representatives of each major group using OASIS, to which the developers would regularly report, presenting current work and the plans. This board should evaluate coherence of plans with the users’ needs and its decision-making power on the developers will be limited to such aspects.

In line with the bottom-up approach, the advisory board should also help recognize and favour geographically distributed interactions at the working level if/when they happen. In other words, the board should not “push things” but make sure that “things that work are pulled”.

The existence of an advisory board would give a place where to regularly discuss the long-term evolution of the coupler, in the exascale perspective. In this respect, the role of the advisory board would be to ensure that expertise is shared between the groups and that efforts spent in the different groups converge toward the development of common exascale software. The board should regularly analyse at a more strategic level the effort invested in the coupling infrastructure and this analysis could lead to an organised community investment, possibly through ENES.

A user committee with representatives of each major group using OASIS to collect the needs and requirements of end users, to directly inform the developers and to provide feedback on technical issues. Members would be responsible for collecting the needs and feedbacks from their own group. Means to get inputs from the whole community will have to be implemented. In practice, the user committee and the advisory board could be composed of the same people. The frequency of formal interaction between the different stakeholders (user committee with developers, developers with advisory board, advisory board with developers) should be of the order of once a year. In between, informal communication would continue to be encouraged as now.

Technical level: no formal governance. A small number of developers interact strongly and is in charge of coupler evolution and related technical choices. Users provide feedback on technical issues. Developers have decision-making power over financial resources (in future external funding scenarios this power would stay the same, within the governance of the external funding programme that should be coordinated, as far as possible, with the coupler governance).

The implementation of this plan is foreseen within ESIWACE.

User support:

In the frame of IS-ENES2, support services for OASIS include easy access to OASIS software sources, trainings and personal help to efficiently use the software. For details, please refer to the OASIS homepage, which also offers documentation, tutorial, FAQs and user forums. These services will be maintained within ESIWACE.

Funding model:

Supported by Cerfacs and CNRS with national (ANR) and EC fundings for some specific developments and service.

3.2 CDO

Name: CDO

Short Description:

The Climate Data Operators (CDO) software is a collection of command line operators to manipulate and analyse Climate and NWP model Data. The operators include simple statistical and arithmetic functions, data selection and subsampling tools, and spatial interpolation. Apart from that CDO can be used to analyse any kind of gridded data not related to climate science. Supported data formats are GRIB 1/2, netCDF 3/4, SERVICE, EXTRA and IEG. There are more than 600 operators available.

Current version(s) of the software in the frame of ESIWACE (as of Feb 2016):

CDO Version 1.7.1

Developer:

Uwe Schulzweida, Ralf Müller, MPI-M/MPG (Hamburg, Germany)

Documentation available at:

<https://code.zmaw.de/projects/cdo/wiki/Cdo#Documentation>

Contact:

Via Reinhard Budich (MPI-M): reinhard.budich@mpimet.mpg.de

Target community (type, size, and geographic distribution):

Worldwide climate and numerical weather prediction community. The CDOs have been downloaded several ten thousand times during the last two years.

Governance:

The CDO is under constant development in close cooperation with stakeholders from the climate research community. Development requests are issued via the user forum – including a ticket system - of the CDOs, and met via a best-effort approach. The software is an open-source project maintained in a master subversion repository at MPI-M. It is managed through the web-based Redmine project management system. The CDO software is published under the terms of the GNU General Public License, version 2.

Foreseen developments (specify which activities are developed within ESIWACE):

The current focus of the development lies on Climate Model Output Rewriter (CMOR) compatibility in order to harmonize post-processing output data formats. CMOR is a library to facilitate standardized climate model output and will reduce the effort required to prepare and manage data, e.g. in the context of CMIP6 MIPs.

User support:

Support services for CDO include the CDO helpdesk and webserver and maintaining up-to-date documentation and FAQ on the CDO home page: <https://code.zmaw.de/projects/cdo/wiki>.

Funding model:

MPI für Meteorologie funded the development of the CDOs since their beginnings (About 15 FTEs). Additional funding for the organisation of the user forum and some supportive activity – see User support - has come from the IS-ENES projects and the DKRZ, respectively.

3.3 XIOS

Name: XIOS

Short Description:

Parallel I/O and "in situ" post-treatment for big data in climate modelling.

XIOS addresses flexibility in management of I/O and data definition, using an external XML file parsed at runtime, tackles I/O performance issues, with a dedicated Parallel and Asynchronous I/O server and solves post-treatment issues by integrating internal parallel workflow and dataflow, with the possibility of performing post-treatment "in situ".

Current version(s) of the software in the frame of ESIWACE (as of Feb 2016):

XIOS2

Developer:

CEA - Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives (Saclay, France), IPSL Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace (France).

Documentation available at:

<http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver>

Contact:

Yann Meurdesoif (CEA): yann.meurdesoif@lsce.ipsl.fr
xios-team@forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr

Target community (type, size, and geographic distribution):

Climate modeling and NWP modeling community. XIOS is used by an increasing variety of models: in France it is in-built by default in the IPSL climate models (NEMO, LMDZ, ORCHIDEE, INCA, DYNAMICO), LGGE (MAR) and Ifremer (ROMS, MARS). XIOS implementation in the MétéoFrance / CNRM models (Gelato, Surfec, Arpège climat – used for the CMIP experiments-) is in progress, whereas it is under evaluation in case of the European models of the MetOffice (Hadgem, MONC, Gung-Ho), and ECMWF (IFS, EC-EARTH).

Governance:

XIOS is a 5 years old open source (CeCILL License) software.

The developer team (CEA, Université Pierre et Marie Curie, CNRS- Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique) members meet twice a month to discuss strategic and technical issues. Exchange with the user community takes place on a single user basis by email, or openly by means of dedicated user lists (see User Support).

Foreseen developments (specify which activities are developed within ESIWACE):

In the frame of ESIWACE several development activities - both technical and in terms of user-support- are foreseen. The switch to a fully multithreaded support (OpenMP) will make XIOS suitable for multi-core architectures, is foreseen. The development of model coupling functionalities will lead XIOS and the

coupler OASIS to eventually converge in the same tool. XIOS will also be adapted to support GRIB2 format.

As the use of XIOS server is constantly increasing in the climate modeling community, the user support ESIWACE's user support paradigm will reach beyond the current help-desk, by proposing an online forum, a user guide, tutorials, FAQs, training events and the publication of hints for best practices, with the goal of a more efficient troubleshooting and of a transparent integration of specific user requirements in the software. These activities will also imply a strengthening of the, currently informal, governance structure.

User support:

Three dedicated mailing lists assist the users and guarantee tailored feedback tackling strategic, development and user-experience related issues, respectively:

xios-team@forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr

xios-dev@forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr

xios-users@forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr

Reported bugs are fixed as quickly as possible.

Until now, specific new user requirements are related to CMOR and CF compliance for NetCDF output files that are needed for future CMIP6 simulations. IPSL and CNRM plan to output CMIP6 data files and make the associated post-treatment using only XIOS, in particular, to automatically generate times series without the need to concatenate files. A new feature was requested by the Met Office for the Gung-Ho/LFric project, i.e. the support of the NetCDF ugrid convention for output files.

A XIOS2 users training event has taken place in December 2015 and another one is planned for 2016.

Funding model:

Besides on permanent staff, the development and maintenance of XIOS heavily relies on external projects at French national (ANR grant: CONVERGENCE), European (IS-ENES, IS-ENES2, ESIWACE, EoCoE) and global scale (G8 grant: ICOMEX).

3.4 Cylc

Name: Cylc

Short Description:

Cylc ("silk") is a workflow engine and meta-scheduler. It specialises in continuous workflows of cycling (repeating) tasks such as those used in weather and climate forecasting and research, but it can also be used with non-cycling systems.

Current version(s) of the software in the frame of ESIWACE (as of Feb 2016):

Cylc 6.9.1

Developers:

NIWA (New Zealand), Met Office (UK)

Documentation available at:

<http://cylc.github.io/cylc/>

Contact:

The Met Office Cylc team (metomi@metoffice.gov.uk)

Target community (type, size, and geographic distribution):

Climate modelling and NWP communities internationally ranging from operational weather prediction and seasonal prediction to research users. There are 10 institutions using or evaluating Cylc.

Governance:

Cylc is free software under the GNU GPL v3 license.

Cylc uses the powerful Git distributed source code management system. Git makes branching and merging, forking/cloning, and pushing and pulling changes between repositories very easy. The cylc repository is hosted on GitHub.

The integrator or fork and pull model of distributed development is used. Developers fork the master repository on GitHub, and clone their fork to their local workstation. Changes are pushed to the developer fork and a pull request issued to the master repository, where the core cylc developers review and merge them.

Foreseen developments (specify which activities are developed within ESIWACE):

Development tickets are managed here <https://github.com/cylc/cylc/issues>. The following are driven by the needs of the EsiWACE community.

1. Bug fixing: Cylc is being used for an ever increasing breadth of activities and new platforms. Bugs will inevitably emerge and responding quickly to these is a priority for the development team.
2. Migration of some Rose functionality into cylc (<https://github.com/metomi/rose>): From the first IS-ENES2 workflow workshop, it is clear that many of the ESIWACE community are likely to be primarily interested in cylc and will not want to also use Rose, a separate set of tools developed at the Met Office to complement cylc, at least initially. Hence, support for suite installation and a web interface for viewing suite output will be moved into cylc from Rose. Any cylc users not already using Rose will find these new features of significant benefit. This also has architectural benefits as incorporating these features into cylc should make them easier to maintain and make it easier to develop future enhancements.
3. Cylc scalability: Based on feedback within the current user community, we need to allow cylc to scale to meet the needs of larger computing platforms and increasingly complex workflows to support activities such as ensemble weather prediction and operational seasonal prediction systems. We will optimise the suite daemon to reduce memory footprint, speed up the scheduling algorithm and provide an efficient data storage model to document the full lifetime of a running suite. This work will ensure that cylc is fast and robust and does not become a bottleneck for computing resources.
4. Modernisation: Ease of installation and conformance with organisational technical constraints is increasingly important as cylc is deployed to more institutions. The team will update the communications layer to use a RESTful API via HTTP to replace the current mechanism based on RPC. Another driver for this is ensuring that cylc is not limited by Pyro3 - a legacy Python remote object library which is no longer maintained.

User support:

Provided by the Met Office within the limits of ESIWACE funding.

Funding model:

Core cylc development is funded by NIWA and the Met Office with additional funding from within ESIWACE.

3.5 NEMO

Name: NEMO

Short Description:

Modelling framework for oceanographic research, operational oceanography seasonal forecast, and climate studies.

NEMO includes 5 major components (ocean dynamics: NEMO-OPA, sea-ice: NEMO-LIM, biogeochemistry: NEMO-TOP, adaptive mesh refinement software: AGRIF, assimilation component NEMO-OBS and -TAM), some reference configurations allowing to set-up and validate the applications (<http://www.nemo-ocean.eu/Using-NEMO/Configurations>), and a set of scripts and tools (including pre- and post-processing) to use the system.

Current version(s) of the software in the frame of ESIWACE (as of Feb 2016):

NEMO_v3_6_STABLE, released June 2015:

http://www.nemo-ocean.eu/About-NEMO/News/NEMO-release-nemo_v3_6_STABLE-available

Developer:

NEMO Consortium: CMCC Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (Italy), CNRS (France), INGV Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia (Italy), MetOffice (UK), Mercator-Ocean (France), NOC National Oceanography Centre (UK).

Documentation available at:

<http://www.nemo-ocean.eu>

Contact:

Sébastien Masson (UPMC, France) sebastien.masson@locean-ipsl.upmc.fr

Claire Lévy (CNRS, France) claire.levy@locean-ipsl.upmc.fr

Target community (type, size, and geographic distribution):

NEMO is used by 200 projects and 1300 registered users worldwide (half of which in Europe) for oceanographic research, operational forecasts (as in Copernicus CMEMS) and climate studies, see <http://www.nemo-ocean.eu/About-NEMO/Projects>. It is the ocean component model used in 5 of the 7 European ESMs in play for the MIPs experiments in IPCC.

Governance model:

NEMO source code is released under the CeCILL license.

NEMO is organized through a Consortium. As written in the Consortium Agreement:

"Purpose of the Consortium: The purpose of this Agreement is to set up appropriate arrangements for the successful and sustainable development of the NEMO System as a well-organized, state-of-the-art ocean model code system suitable for both research and operational work."

The Consortium relies on the following bodies: System Team, NEMO officers (one per institution of the Consortium), Working Groups, Project Manager, Scientific Leader, Developers Committee and Steering Committee.

We report here briefly about the strategic role of each body as indicated in the NEMO consortium agreement (signed in 2008 and updated in 2011).

Steering Committee: decision-making and arbitration body (one representative from each Consortium Member, Scientific Leader, Project Manager, director of LOCEAN), deciding and agreeing on: strategic direction of the Project; appointment of Project Manager, Scientific Leader and NEMO System Team Coordinator; yearly work-plan; contributions Consortium Members to the work-plan, financial commitments; principles of distribution of non national handing supporting the NEMO System Team; approval on an annual basis of members of Developers Committee and Working Groups (as proposed by Project Manager and Scientific Leader); modification to the Consortium Agreement; approval on an annual basis of the list of personnel assigned to the NEMO System Team; inclusion or expulsion of Consortium Members; settlement of disputes. The Steering Committee normally meets once a year; the NEMO Project Manager or any Consortium Member may request extraordinary meetings.

The chairperson of the Steering Committee is the representative of CNRS-INSU. The chairperson sets the agenda for the meetings and ensures that decisions taken by the Steering Committee have been implemented. The chairperson shall draft the minutes of each meeting to formalize all decisions taken and dispatch them to all Consortium Members.

Each Consortium Member representative on the Steering Committee will be eligible to vote on matters concerning the Consortium. This person may not be the NEMO Scientific Leader or the NEMO Project Manager. All decisions will be taken by unanimous vote.

System Team: (experts on the NEMO system coordinated by the NEMO System Team Coordinator) to develop, distribute and support NEMO reference and its evolutions.

NEMO System Team experts are coming from the consortium's institution (consortium Agreement states that each institution dedicates a minimum of one man-year for System team). On the developer's side, the System Team ensures the sustainable development of NEMO.

On the user side, the System Team ensures the user support on the NEMO reference, including the reference configurations (but not all the configurations build and used by specific projects).

The System Team carries out agreed plan and schedule of work approved by the steering committee, incorporation of new developments (scientific or technical), re-organisation of code to improve its readability, orthogonality or structure, optimisation of NEMO on the computers available in the consortium, maintenance of the paper and on-line documentation, configuration control of the available versions, testing and release of new versions (typically once a year), making NEMO readily available to the scientific community and members of the consortium, providing user assistance, support for user meetings (held typically once every two years), assistance in scientific development.

Scientific Leader and System Team Coordinator: to develop scientific and technical knowledge within the NEMO System Team; to clarify scientific and technical priorities for development; to ensure timely and appropriate reviews of proposed contributions to the code; to publicize the Consortium and seek funding opportunities.

Project Manager: to coordinate input to and agreement of the annual work plan for the Team and Working Groups; to write a coordinated summary of the work on the System planned by other Consortium Members; to maintain regular contact between Team members and encourage constructive team working; to monitor progress and report exceptions to the work plan to the chairperson of the Steering Committee; to report to the Steering Committee on progress in the previous year and work plan for next year; to organize users' meeting; to propose to the Steering Committee Developers Committee members on an annual basis.

NEMO Developers Committee (leading ocean modeling scientists having complementary and necessary expertise for NEMO development): to ensure that most useful developments in research and operational community are integrated into NEMO; to give advice on research developments plan; to

coordinate developments planned by scientists outside the Team, and in particular to coordinate them with the Team work-plan; to set up working groups, appoint their leaders and validate the report drafted by the working group; to propose opportunities for funding to the Steering Committee.

The list of members shall be approved on an annual basis by the Steering Committee. According to the agenda, any expert, upon suggestion by the NEMO System Team, may be invited to attend Developers Committee meetings. The Developers Committee is chaired by the NEMO Scientific Leader and by the NEMO Project Manager.

Working Groups: in 2016, the active Working groups are: Assimilation, Configuration Manager, AGRIF, Wave coupling, HPC, Robustness and test cases, see <https://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/nemo/wiki/WorkingGroups>.

NEMO has a development -covering natural and computer science aspects - strategy on mid to long-term (5-10 years), see <http://www.nemo-ocean.eu/About-NEMO/News/Development-Strategy-2014>, reviewed and updated each year if relevant.

Foreseen developments (specify which activities are developed within ESIWACE):

In the frame of IS-ENES2 activities on NEMO performance (scalability, porting, testing) are in progress. The developments foreseen within ESIWACE build on this legacy. The code optimization work will benefit moreover from the experience of the Center for Excellence in parallel programming of BULL. The development of a hybrid version (based on MPI and OpenMP) of NEMO has started and is based on the last official release of the code.

The compute/communication performance of NEMO (as component of EC-Earth3.2 using the OASIS3-MCT), with analysis tools that employ adequate tracing protocols (benefitting from pre-ESIWACE work carried out by BSC in collaboration with the NEMO System Team) will be assessed.

The work on concurrency and accuracy investigates the possibility in NEMO of de-sequencing and thus enhancing concurrency between the ocean dynamics and the sea-ice and surface processes, thereby increasing the parallelism of NEMO. A report (Maisonave and Masson, 2015) describes the technical implementation and first tests validating the concurrent execution of these components and the related gain in performance.

Within ESIWACE, the services supported by IS-ENES2 (creation and maintenance of NEMO reference experiments database) will be further pursued and enhanced, facilitating community wide access and use of NEMO latest versions, including version control and ticketing system, diffusing best practices and accelerating the update cycle.

User support:

NEMO is available as a source code, after registration on the NEMO web site, and agreement of the license. 6 reference configurations are currently available, with their downloadable input files.

The NEMO reference database (assembled during IS-ENES: <https://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/nemo/wiki/NEMOConfigurationDataBase>), freely accessible upon registration, is currently being maintained and enriched, in the frame of IS-ENES2, by results produced by the code including new developments run with the historical (ORCA2) configuration but also at higher resolution (e.g. ORCA025) and by experiments activating the NEMO LIM3 sea-ice subcomponent at high resolution, after proper calibration and validation when forced with atmospheric reanalyses. This database illustrates the diversity of the simulations that can be achieved with NEMO, helping the users to understand the processes at stake in ocean modeling and to select the most appropriate set of parameters and physical packages for their ESM and will moreover help the NEMO large community of users to better evaluate their ocean simulations.

With the NEMO code and its history, users can find on the NEMO website (upon registration) information (documentation, user guide, FAQ, literature, list of the projects), dedicated forum pages, archives of the users mailing list, and newsletter. Users are asked to upload their own articles using NEMO, which is an efficient way to support the work of the System Team.

Users can rely moreover on two mailing lists `nemo_st@locean-ipsl.upmc.fr` (the NEMO System Team) and `nemo@locean-ipsl.upmc.fr` (the whole users community) to provide feedback to the System Team and to reach all users, respectively. A TRAC system is also available to open tickets for debugging. Training courses are put in place for new users or on specific topics. Users meetings are also an opportunity for users to meet the System Team and exchange on their expertise, needs and difficulties.

Funding model:

The consortium's institutions are joining their experts to build the NEMO System Team, which is the foundation of NEMO's development.

NEMO is directly involved in a number of European projects focusing on applications or services, including IS-ENES, IS-ENES2, and ESIWACE. Opportunities for external funding are sought by the Scientific Leader and Project Manager, discussed by the Developer Team and submitted to the Steering Committee.

3.6 EC-Earth/OpenIFS

Name: EC-Earth/OpenIFS

Short Description:

EC-Earth is a state-of-the-art earth system model that is developed by a European consortium of 27 research institutes in 10 countries. The GCM core of EC-Earth is made of the IFS/OpenIFS atmosphere, coupled to the NEMO ocean using OASIS. Additional components are available to provide for a fully coupled Atmosphere-Ocean-Land-Biosphere model.

Current version(s) of the software in the frame of ESIWACE (as of Feb 2016):

EC-Earth 3.2beta

Developer:

The EC-Earth Consortium

Documentation available at:

<http://www.ec-earth.org>

Contact:

Peter Bauer (ECMWF): peter.bauer@ecmwf.int

Uwe Fladrich (SMHI): uwe.fladrich@smhi.se

Target community (type, size, and geographic distribution):

European climate modelling community, with a current user/developer base distributed over 27 institutions and 10 countries.

Governance:

EC-Earth is governed by a Steering Committee (SC), representing the partners that have signed a Memorandum of Understanding. Remaining partner institutions have signed a Letter of Intent. The consortium is organised in Working Groups (WG), which represent the major strategic foci of model development and scientific application. The International EC-Earth Meetings are held 9-monthly and provide a platform for WG reporting and strategic planning.

Foreseen developments (specify which activities are developed within ESIWACE):

Transition from IFS to OpenIFS as the atmospheric component of EC-Earth and corresponding upgrade of the IFS cycle. Assessment of XIOS as an (optional) I/O subsystem for OpenIFS and, provided a positive outcome, integration of XIOS in OpenIFS.

User support:

EC-Earth maintains an external web site for general information about the model and the consortium. For EC-Earth users and developers the consortium maintains a Development Portal, which provides means of collaborative model development. This comprises a version control repository, an issue tracking system, discussion forums, and Wiki pages. Regular software releases help users to keep up with the model development.

Funding model:

In kind contributions of partner institutes.

4. Summary and Outlook

The list above shows a portfolio of software shared among climate and weather modellers - first category of our Methodology section-, but heterogeneous in terms of genesis, function, development stage and governance. The way software is organized in phase of design, development and adaptation/correction/enhancement upon user feedback could be very different, even when the communities of user (and/or of stakeholders) overlap. Elaborated governance structures workflows indicate 'mature' software, heritage of several other projects before and in parallel to ESIWACE (as, to date, it is the case of NEMO or EC-Earth, both involving international consortia, and of OASIS, currently implementing its governance). A simpler structure governs the tools whose development is concentrated at one partner's institution or carried out by a restricted number of people (XIOS, Cylc, CDO). Awareness on all these structures will help in guiding and channeling ESIWACE developments. ESIWACE will not intervene redefining well-codified decision-making workflows, but could contribute to strengthen the existing governance structures by strengthening and enhancing the interaction with the users.

Beyond this very document, the ESIWACE government will gather information on other software belonging to the second and third group introduced above in the methodology: existing software showing the potential of becoming community tool (e.g. the experiment manager Autosubmit <http://autosubmit.ic3.cat/>, developed in the frame of IS-ENES2), and newly developed codes. The goal is to obtain a state-of-the-art sketch of what the community uses, needs and might need striving towards improvements in scalability and usability of models and tools and in the exploitability of storage systems.

The submission of a questionnaire to the ESIWACE network of supporting institutions will be the instrument to ignite discussion and result in a software list. Such list will be kept as a "living document", i.e. frequently updated, implying continuous consultation with codes and tools stakeholder, steering and user groups. Also for this list, to different levels of maturity of the items will correspond different needs

in terms of activities to be implemented within and beyond ESIWACE. This new software list will complement this document D1.1, constituting a support instrument to the project governance, all along the project lifetime, to establish criteria and procedures for prioritizing user requirements and accordingly orienting planned activities, or inspiring activities in projects or initiatives to come. For this software as well, the underlining idea is not to take over the existing governance, nor to allocate extra resources, non-foreseen within ESIWACE.

In subordinate level of priority, groups could also indicate other common software (belonging to the fourth group), to make the picture even more thorough.

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